

The LINKed Data Asset for Australian Health Research (LINDAHR)

ARDC AUSTRALIAN DATA PARTNERSHIPS PROGRAM
PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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30/11/2023

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1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	DP793
PROJECT START AND END DATES	Jan 2021 - Dec 2023
LEAD ORGANISATION	UNSW
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	<p> AIHW Australian Government Department of Health Queensland Health NSW Health Population Health Research Network University of Technology Sydney University of Sydney University of Melbourne Monash University Bond University The University of Queensland University of Western Australia Curtin University Australian National University University of Tasmania University of South Australia The George Institute for Global Health Hunter Medical Research Institute Baker Heart and Diabetes Institute Burnet Institute Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre QIMR Berghofer Medical Research Institute Telethon Kids Institute Murdoch Children’s Research Institute </p>
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1.1 Background

Internationally, there is increasing use of linked routinely collected health care data to improve human health and health care outcomes. However, Australia's health researchers do not have streamlined access to linked comprehensive cross-jurisdictional administrative health and social data. This results in lost opportunities for research to improve health care practices and health outcomes. There is no published information on the requirements and preferences of Australian researchers for content, governance and access arrangements for enduring linked data assets, or the secure access environments in which they are accessed.

The Linked Data Asset for Australian Health Research (LINDAHR) project is a partnership between the Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW) and academic researchers. It was proposed to facilitate the co-design of streamlined researcher access to the AIHW's enduring linked cross-jurisdictional public sector health and social datasets, as well as the future integration of high-value investigator-initiated health datasets such as registries, cohort studies and clinical trials. LINDAHR was proposed to support robust cross-jurisdictional research assessing the safety, quality, equity and value of health care and policies such as studies of rare diseases and priority populations. An enduring linked health and social data asset would enable timely and cost-effective research that would reduce harm and improve our surveillance and crisis responses.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

The LINDAHR project aimed to establish researcher access to an enduring linked data asset maintained by the [Australian Institute of Health and Welfare \(AIHW\)](#), and ensure it was supported by appropriate governance and infrastructure. The project also aimed to enable the progressive linkage and integration of high-value, population health, medical and social datasets.

The project achieved researcher access to AIHW's [National Integrated Health Services Information \(NIHSI\) Analysis Asset](#). The NIHSI is a longitudinal, person focussed, de-identified enduring linked health data collection containing State and Territory hospital separation, Medicare Benefits Schedule (MBS), Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme (PBS) and Repatriation Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme (RPBS), Residential Aged Care Services and National Death Index data. The NIHSI was historically only accessible to Government users. The LINDAHR project established new streamlined governance processes, NIHSI data access via the Australian Bureau of Statistics' Secure Environment for Analysing Data (SEAD), a cost-recovery model for researcher access and use, resources for code sharing, and a data sharing agreement template for integrating researcher datasets. As a result, Australian researchers are now able to safely and more efficiently access and use linked cross-jurisdictional health data.

Long-term sustainability of the NIHSI data asset will be ensured through the AIHW's plan to evolve and transition the NIHSI to the National Health Data Hub (NHDH), a broader health data access and integration system. The NHDH will expand the datasets available to researchers with new health and social datasets expected to be progressively added to the NIHSI in tranches. The NHDH is eventually expected to become the health domain asset in the Australian National Data Integration Infrastructure (ANDII).

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1 Achievements against project work packages:

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION (INCLUDE LINKS TO RELEVANT DOCUMENTATION)	COMPLETION DATE
1.1 Draft data management plan	A draft data management plan (DMP) was developed. We sourced publicly available resources for traditional data collections. The draft plan was based around the key elements of the Five Safes Framework.	18/08/2021
1.2 Revise data management plan	The AIHW published a Data Quality Statement (DQS) for the NIHSI v1.0 on their metadata online registry (METeOR). The DQS covers most of what is traditionally included in a DMP, including timeliness, accessibility, interpretability, relevance, accuracy and coherence of the data asset and therefore will replace the need for a DMP. The DQS for future versions of the NIHSI will be published on the AIHW website when available.	23/09/2022
1.3 Collect information about data asset users (incl ORCIDs)	This information is being collected by AIHW as part of their standard processes. Information on approved projects is available on the AIHW website and will be continuously updated as more projects are approved.	11/08/2023
1.4 Researcher survey	Researchers were surveyed to understand user experience and feedback on the NIHSI information available on the AIHW website. Results will be used to inform future development of the NIHSI.	30/11/2023
1.5 Assign DOI to asset	A DOI has been assigned to the NIHSI DQS v1.0. This DOI will be activated by AIHW prior to launch of the NHDH website in February 2024. Since the information will be updated as the NIHSI/NHDH evolves, subsequent versions of the DQS' will be assigned new DOIs.	29/02/2024

<p>1.6 Publish data asset in RDA</p>	<p>A NIHSI/NHDH record linking back to the AIHW website will be added to the Research Data Australia registry by AIHW following launch of the NHDH website in February 2024.</p>	<p>29/02/2024</p>
<p>1.7 Set up template reports for tracking citations to data asset</p>	<p>This is embedded in the AIHW output approval process. Links to AIHW reports and researcher outputs that have used NIHSI data (e.g. PubMed articles, and reports on other websites) will be available on the AIHW website.</p>	<p>30/11/2023</p>
<p>2.1 Identify all relevant datasets, existing agreements & custodians; determine the highest priority datasets to be included in the asset</p>	<p>Datasets held by AIHW were identified and prioritised. Existing agreements between AIHW and data custodians were identified.</p> <p>As the scope of LINDAHR evolved over the course of the project, additional datasets were identified, prioritised and considered for inclusion by AIHW, including state/territory datasets.</p> <p>AIHW are planning to integrate additional datasets into the NHDH via a tiered approach, including investigator-initiated datasets such as Clinical Quality Registries (CQRs).</p>	<p>30/06/2021</p>
<p>2.2 Stakeholder consultations and roundtables to ascertain requirements, barriers and priorities</p>	<p>Four focus group sessions comprising of health researchers were held to discuss researcher requirements for an enduring national linked data asset for Australian health research. The discussions focussed on datasets, data access, reproducibility, governance, management, and sustainability issues. The report summarising focus group discussion findings was finalised on 13 November 2021.</p> <p>A researcher survey was conducted in early 2022 to further ascertain researcher requirements. A summary report outlining the outcomes of the survey was developed.</p>	<p>15/08/2022</p>
<p>2.3 Establish data custodian data use and access requirements, including positioning for future uses</p>	<p>Consultations with public sector data custodians to ascertain their perspectives and requirements for researcher access to enduring linked health data assets, within the context of broader data integration infrastructure developments were completed. A high-level statement of public sector requirements was drafted. Further specific requirements of individual data custodians will be reflected in governance arrangements for the National Health Data Hub (NHDH).</p>	<p>30/11/2022</p>

<p>2.4 Establish research sector data use and access requirements, including future uses</p>	<p>See 2.2. Researcher data use and access requirements were explored as part of the focus groups.</p>	<p>31/03/2022</p>
<p>2.5 Draft agreement for new national linked health data asset, including the future addition of investigator-initiated datasets</p>	<p>A new national linked data asset was not created. Instead, streamlined governance processes and arrangements were established to give researchers access to the AIHW's existing NIHSI data asset. These arrangements are outlined within the NIHSI governance protocols approved by the AIHW Ethics Committee and the NIHSI Advisory Committee. In parallel, Australian governments are actively working to design more streamlined approaches for national data sharing and integration and the creation of enduring data assets, an example being the ANDII/National Disability Data Asset (NDDA) project currently underway. The AIHW are also working to transition the NIHSI to a broader health data integration and access system (NHDH), which will also enable the integration of other priority datasets.</p>	<p>28/02/2023</p>
<p>2.6 Negotiate and finalise agreement for new national linked health data asset</p>	<p>The AIHW Ethics Committee and the NIHSI Advisory Committee endorsed and approved the streamlined governance arrangements to enable non-Government researcher access to the NIHSI.</p>	<p>28/02/2023</p>
<p>2.7 Obtain ethical approval for creation of new data asset</p>	<p>The AIHW Ethics Committee approved non-Government researcher access to the NIHSI in February 2023.</p>	<p>28/02/2023</p>
<p>2.8 Obtain Public Interest Certificate</p>	<p>This is no longer required as an existing AIHW asset will be leveraged. The AIHW has obtained a Public Interest Certificate (PIC) for Medical Benefits Schedule (MBS)/Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme (PBS) data for the NIHSI and the requirements for any further PICs will be determined through the development of the NHDH.</p>	<p>31/10/2022</p>
<p>2.9 Finalise data access framework and data sharing agreements</p>	<p>Under the streamlined access model, data sharing agreements (DSAs) are not required for researcher access to public sector datasets in the NIHSI.</p> <p>A DSA template to support the future integration of researcher datasets with the NIHSI was developed. AIHW are</p>	<p>31/08/2023</p>

	<p>considering the recommendations arising from stakeholder consultations on the integration of researcher-initiated datasets into NIHSI, as detailed in the report prepared by the contractor overseeing the consultations (HealthConsult).</p>	
<p>2.10 Proof of concept LINDAHR</p>	<p>No longer required as the NIHSI served this purpose.</p>	<p>31/12/2022</p>
<p>2.11 Stakeholder consultations and roundtables</p>	<p>See 2.2. Stakeholder consultations were undertaken as part of the data sharing agreements work to understand researcher requirements and perspectives on the integration of investigator-initiated datasets to the NIHSI.</p> <p>The NIHSI and its transition to the NHDH were promoted at conferences including the Health Services Research Association of Australia and New Zealand (HSRAANZ) in 2022 and the Australasian Epidemiological Association Annual Scientific Meeting (AEA ASM) in 2023.</p>	<p>19/10/2023</p>
<p>2.12 Operationalise LINDAHR</p>	<p>The objectives of the LINDAHR project have been achieved through the expansion of the NIHSI to allow researcher access via the Secure Environment for Analysing Data (SEAD) and supported by streamlined governance arrangements. Researchers can now apply to access NIHSI data, as per instructions, resources and the project proposal form provided on the AIHW website.</p> <p>AIHW will continue to transition the NIHSI to the NHDH which will fully realise the LINDAHR objectives through a greater range of datasets available and processes in place to support the integration of investigator-initiated datasets.</p>	<p>30/11/2023</p>
<p>3.1 Stakeholder consultations and roundtables to ascertain requirements, barriers and priorities</p>	<p>See 2.2 and 2.3. Data processing and curation pipelines were discussed in the focus groups and researcher survey.</p>	<p>15/08/2022</p>

3.2 Identify and finalise data pipeline use cases, including future use	AIHW's existing data pipelines will be used for current public sector datasets and future investigator-initiated datasets.	11/08/2023
3.3 Draft and finalise data pipeline business case for AIHW's SRAE	<p>An AIHW instance of the ABS' Secure Environment for Analysing Data (SEAD) was chosen as the secure access environment for the NIHSI, rather than the SRAE, in alignment with the broader future national data integration infrastructure.</p> <p>The data pipeline and secure access environment (SEAD) meet AIHW's protocols. Costs for researcher access and use of the NIHSI, including the SEAD, are on a cost-recovery basis. Costs are available on the AIHW website and will be modified as required. Negotiations are underway to identify potential opportunities to subsidise costs to researchers.</p>	30/11/2023
3.4 Design and build data processing & curation pipelines	See 3.2. The data processing and curation pipelines for the NIHSI follow existing standard operating procedures at AIHW and did not need to be modified.	11/08/2023
4.1 Stakeholder consultations and roundtables to ascertain requirements	See 2.2. Researcher requirements and perspectives around code sharing/publication of syntax were explored in the focus groups and researcher survey.	15/08/2022
4.2 Identify and finalise use cases	Based on advice from code sharing experts and a desktop review, a report outlining how the LINDAHR project could support code sharing was developed.	30/11/2023
4.3 Draft and finalise business case	The code sharing report proposed recommendations and actions for how the LINDAHR project could encourage and support researchers using NIHSI to share their code/syntax.	30/11/2023
4.4 Design, build, test and finalise interface and processes	It was determined it was not necessary to build a new platform as existing platforms are working well. However, materials outlining the processes to share and save code into permanent repositories with the ability to assign DOIs were compiled to support researcher capability and capacity. In addition, all NIHSI approved users can join the AIHW's data integration forum, a Community of Practice where	30/11/2023

	researchers can share and discuss their learnings and best practices.	
5.1 Stakeholder consultations and roundtables to ascertain requirements	See 2.2. Sustainability options were discussed in the focus groups and further explored in the survey.	15/08/2022
5.2 Identify and finalise use cases	Use cases and case studies demonstrating the value and benefit of the NIHSI, and the expansion of the NIHSI for researcher access were developed. These will be available on the AIHW website.	30/11/2023
5.3 Draft and finalise business case	AIHW have pursued multiple avenues for ongoing funding for the NIHSI and NHDH, including seeking Government funding and initiating negotiations with ARDC for potential funding. The current costs for researcher access and use of the NIHSI have been published on the AIHW website .	30/11/2023
5.4 Design, build, test and finalise systems and processes	Expansion of the NIHSI to include researcher access fulfils the LINDAHR project objectives. Researcher access was soft launched in August 2023 and the processes tested.	30/11/2023

2.2 Project outputs

Project Output	Description
Focus group discussion findings report	Report detailing the findings from the focus group sessions conducted in August 2021 to understand researcher requirements and priorities for an enduring linked health data asset.
Researcher survey summary report	Report summarising the results from the online survey conducted with Australian health data linkage researchers to gain a deeper understanding of researcher requirements and preferences for a national enduring linked health data asset.

Code sharing report	This report summarises the barriers and potential solutions for openly sharing code within the context of public health researchers, that were explored throughout this project.
HealthConsult Final Report and Data Sharing Agreement template	To understand researcher perspectives on sharing investigator-initiated data with the NIHSI, an external contractor, HealthConsult, was engaged to conduct stakeholder consultations and develop a draft Data Sharing Agreement that would be used to facilitate this process in the future. HealthConsult produced a final report detailing their consultation findings as well as a Data Sharing Agreement template for AIHW to adapt for use.

2.3 Outreach and training activities

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
NIHSI/SEAD training	Approved user onboarding training to the NIHSI secure access environment. This training provides approved users with an understanding of the system, the NIHSI data design, the approvals and vetting process and the obligations that need to be met by approved users of the secure access environment.	5 to 10 participants on average per session	Held once a month since April 2023
AIHW data integration forum	This forum is for approved users to share issues and ideas with using the NIHSI. As a Community of Practice forum, these meetings are to share lessons learnt and best practice.	170 participants	Quarterly
Version release update presentation	To advise approved users of the changes incorporated in the release.	170 participants	Intermittent – when a release of NIHSI occurs

<p>Health Services Research Association of Australia and New Zealand (HSRAANZ) Annual Scientific Meeting 2022</p>	<p>A LINDAHR symposium session was held at the HSRAANZ 2022 ASM. Presentations on both researcher and public sector perspectives and requirements for enduring national linked health data were given, followed by an introduction by AIHW to the NIHSI and NHDH.</p>	<p>100 participants</p>	<p>1 December 2022</p>
<p>Australasian Epidemiological Association (AEA) Annual Scientific Meeting 2023</p>	<p>A concurrent session on data linkage methods was held at the 2023 AEA conference. The NIHSI, its data linkage methods, and its proposed evolution into the NHDH were introduced to the health researcher audience.</p>	<p>50-100 participants</p>	<p>19 October 2023</p>
<p>HealthConsult engagement</p>	<p>Stakeholder consultations were undertaken with a cross-section of health researchers to understand their perspectives on governance processes, including current arrangements and key considerations for a more streamlined and centralised data-sharing process.</p>	<p>20-30 participants</p>	<p>April – June 2023</p>

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

- Long term utility of the asset in ANDII and NHDH
 - The NIHSI/NHDH holds the AIHW-managed health service National Minimum Datasets (NMDS) which are central to the health data system. The NMDSs are used for reporting, planning, policy development and program management. The NIHSI/NHDH in the future

will link cohort and other datasets to the NIHSI/NDDA, greatly reducing bespoke data linkages. This will be AIHW’s primary data linkage service, reducing bespoke requests. Additionally, the NIHSI/NDDA will enable the distribution of AIHW hospitals NMDs to other assets such as the NDDA. This approach optimises the ‘supply once, multiple use’ data strategy.

- There is commitment to establish the NHDH which will leverage and adopt the existing NIHSI streamlined governance arrangements.
- Seeking ongoing funding from Government
 - AIHW have sought advice from the Department of Health and Aged Care regarding seeking ongoing funding support.
 - Discussions have been held with NIHSI Advisory Committee members regarding seeking ongoing funding for NIHSI.

4 FAIR

4.1 Implementation of FAIR Data Guidelines

FAIR Data Actions

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
1	All data outputs are assigned appropriate PIDs, preferably a DOI	A DOI has been assigned to the NIHSI DQS. As a condition of use of the asset, researchers will be required to cite this DOI in all outputs. As the NIHSI is enduring and not static, new versions of the DQS will be assigned new DOIs.
2	All data outputs have metadata to enable discovery	The DQS for the NIHSI, available on the metadata online registry (METeOR) platform, includes metadata for all contributing datasets. This will be maintained and revised, including further information about additional datasets as they are integrated. A data dictionary is also available to approved users of the NIHSI.
3	All data outputs have a record in Research Data Australia	Note: Not applicable as NIHSI metadata is maintained by the AIHW on their METeOR platform.
4	All data outputs are	Note: Not applicable.

	registered with relevant discipline-specific discovery aggregators (Recommended , if they exist)	
5	The persistent identifier for the data output being described is included in the metadata	The persistent identifier is included in the metadata (DQS).
6	All data outputs are made as openly available as possible; they are only closed where necessary	Note: As LINDAHR/NIHSI contains sensitive linked health data there are restrictions to access in line with the Five Safes Framework. Only analysts approved for specific approved projects, in line with the agreed uses, will be able to access the data through the secure access environment (SEAD). The publication of aggregate data outputs will be supported and, as is standard practice for data of this kind, require prior data custodian review.
7	All data outputs are made available through a repository	NIHSI data is available for access by approved researchers in a secure access environment (SEAD).
8	All data outputs are available as a download and/or accessible through an open, documented API (where data is not closed)	Note: Not applicable due to legislative requirements about data contained in the asset. See 6 above.
9	If the data outputs are not openly available, there is a clear description on the landing page on how to request access to the data outputs and the conditions that need to be met	The landing page on the AIHW website includes the process for requesting access and the conditions that must be met for researcher access.
10	The persistent identifier for the data output points to a landing page about the data output, even if the data output is not	A persistent identifier will be assigned to the NIHSI DQS. As a condition of use, all aggregate data outputs (i.e., reports, journal articles) will be assigned a persistent identifier.

	public (open).	
11	If the data output is not openly available there is an authorisation and authentication procedure to provide access to the data	Authorisation and authentication will be provided through AIHW as part of their approvals processes.
12	The persistent identifier for the data output continues to point to a landing page, even if the data output is no longer available, and there is a policy to maintain these landing pages	If no longer available, AIHW will tombstone the landing page. The landing page is separate to access to the data; it will give a link to how to apply for access to data, even if it changes over time.
13	Data outputs use community-agreed standard data formats (where such agreed formats exist)	Data dictionaries are available for the component datasets. The quality of these may vary and NIHSI will rely on the existing data dictionaries for the underlying datasets.
14	Metadata for the data output uses community-agreed standards (where such agreed standards exist)	Note: Not applicable as this is outside the scope of this project, which is limited to (existing) metadata of the established component datasets.
15	Data and metadata use community-agreed vocabularies, data models and ontologies (Recommended , preferably internationally agreed ones where they exist)	Note: Not applicable as this is outside the scope of this project which brings together existing datasets. We acknowledge the value of standard vocabularies and mapping to a common data model may be explored in the future.
16	Metadata contains persistent identifiers for research objects and entities (people,	Note: Not currently relevant. The current NIHSI integrates public sector datasets. With the future inclusion of researcher-initiated datasets, these requirements will be met.

	organisations) linked to the data outputs (including ORCIDs, grantIDs, RAIDs, DOIs, IGSNs)	
17	All data outputs are assigned a machine readable licence (preferably CC-BY 4.0)	Note: The responsibility for the NIHSI/NHDH lies with the AIHW. Researchers will be able to propose projects to use the data asset, and once approved, researchers will need to sign undertakings related to use of the asset. There will not be a license as such for use of the asset.
18	The licence information is available in a machine readable form on the landing page that the persistent identifier (for the data output) refers to	Note: Not applicable.
19	There is a citation statement for the data output on the landing page that the persistent identifier refers to	All outputs from projects that use the NIHSI will be required to acknowledge and cite the NIHSI and its persistent identifier as the data source.
20	Provenance information on the data output is attached alongside the data (Recommended)	Note: Not applicable as data access will only be possible in the secure access environment and provenance information will be provided to prospective applicants.
21	Relevant discipline-specific metadata to enable reuse is captured and presented alongside the data output following research community best practice (Recommended)	Researchers will be encouraged and supported via resources to publish their syntax.

5 PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment. Please complete the following sections as relevant to your program.

5.1 Communications and Engagement

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
<p>Focus groups and in-depth interviews with research sector</p>	<p>Focus groups were conducted in August 2021 to understand researcher requirements and priorities for an enduring linked health data asset.</p> <p>In August 2022, in-depth interviews with 5 researchers experienced in the conduct of health data linkage research were conducted as case study examples.</p> <p>In March 2023, HealthConsult was engaged to conduct consultations with a range of stakeholders to understand key researcher requirements for the development of data sharing agreement templates for the sharing of researcher-initiated datasets with the NIHSI.</p>	<p>Focus group outcomes report</p> <p>HealthConsult Final Report</p>
<p>Online surveys</p>	<p>An online survey of health researchers was conducted from December 2021 to February 2022 to capture a wider range of researcher perspectives.</p> <p>A separate online survey was</p>	<p>Researcher survey summary report</p> <p>NIHSI online survey outcomes</p>

	<p>conducted in October 2023 to seek feedback from researchers on information regarding researcher access to the NIHSI and associated costs.</p>	
Conference presentations	<p>A LINDAHR symposium session was held in December 2022 at the annual meeting of the Health Services Research Association of Australia and New Zealand (HSRAANZ).</p> <p>In October 2023, a concurrent session introducing and promoting the NIHSI and NHDH was held at the Australasian Epidemiological Association (AEA) Annual Scientific Meeting.</p>	
AIHW NIHSI website	<p>Information on the NIHSI, including researcher access and the costs involved, is available on the AIHW website.</p>	<p>https://www.aihw.gov.au/reports-data/nihsi</p>
NIHSI DQS	<p>A data quality statement for NIHSI v1 was published.</p>	<p>https://meteor.aihw.gov.au/content/766334</p>

5.2 Research Outcomes Planning

ACTIVITY	DETAILS
<p>Establishment of a monitoring framework (for project outcomes and impacts)</p>	<p>Discussions on the approaches for monitoring project outcomes and impacts have taken place. Options include future NIHSI/NHDH user surveys, tracking of citations using publicly available resources, and active participation in multi-sector discussions about systems to measure impact.</p>

Inputs from research users in design of the infrastructure	Multiple rounds of in-depth engagement with researchers were completed throughout the project.
Partnerships with research translation specialists	Not required for the scope of this project.
Establishment of policies, systems and workflows to track uptake (of project outcomes)	Systems and workflows have been established with the AIHW to track uptake of the project outcomes at periodic intervals.

6 LESSONS LEARNED

6.1 What Went Well?

- Bringing together the public and research sectors to work towards a common goal, which enabled two-way learning about the perspectives, needs, and constraints of both sectors. This also facilitated the building of relationships of trust between the public and research sectors during the project.
- Successful co-design effort resulting in positive outcomes for both the public and research sectors.
 - Integration of non-government researchers' perspectives into NIHSI planning, processes and material and efficient integration of LINDAHR project aims by building on existing infrastructure and processes in place for NIHSI.
- The ability to adapt and leverage parallel work in the face of limited resources and a changing data sharing environment, some of which was accelerated by unmet data needs during the COVID-19 pandemic.
- The provision of expertise and support by ARDC, having a single point of contact within ARDC but being able to draw upon specific expertise from other ARDC members.
- The establishment of a diverse Steering Committee with representation from both the public and research sectors as well as consumer representation was a great source of support and guidance for the project. Positive engagement between project team and members of the LINDAHR Steering Committee, led to insightful advice being discussed.

- Strong communication and frequent meetings between project team members, as well as the alignment of priorities with deliverables and due dates led to successful project outcomes.
- There was effective succession and knowledge transfer of AIHW staff working on the LINDAHR project, despite significant staff turnover.

6.2 What Could be Improved?

- Although the governance structures for the LINDAHR project were effective, the governance structures for the NIHSI asset were already in place and there was limited opportunity for non-government researchers, or community members, to contribute to decision-making regarding arrangements for access to the asset. A model governance structure for data assets of national significance, that provides for broad representation and input, would be very valuable for guiding the ongoing development of such assets and ensuring maximum public value.
- Future partners should be aware of the potential for regular changes in public sector staff; this is not in and of itself a negative as it can bring fresh perspectives and solutions, but it does require a settling-in period.
- For any future grant calls, the budget template in the grant application form should match the format of the financial reports, for ease of tracking.
- The measure of success against each deliverable could be more clearly defined.
- Better alignment of timeframes and project dependencies would have benefitted the stakeholder consultation process.
- Long-term adoption of various project aims, including code sharing, DOIs and interaction with broader data landscape.
- A framework for measuring the ‘impact’ of the project accurately would assist in evaluating its longer-term outcomes.